

Table 1: Primary Studies

Code	Category / Subcategory	Algorithm Technique	Criteria	Dataset			Evaluation Metrics	Study
				Name	Public/Private	Size		
PS1	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy AHP	Others	-	Partially Public	Small	-	[31]
PS2	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy multi-attribute	Others	-	-	-	-	[21]
PS3	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy AHP	Cost Time Business Value	-	Private	-	Complexity	[13]
PS4	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy AHP	Ranking Dependency FR/NFR relation	-	Public	Medium	-	[42]
PS5	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy multi-attribute	Ranking Others	Greer and Ruhe/ Sagrado	Partially Public	Medium	-	[4]
PS6	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy HCV	Ranking	-	-	-	-	[28]
PS7	Fuzzy Logic	Triangular Fuzzy Number	FR/NFR relation	-	Partially Public	Small	-	[19]
PS8	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy Logic	Ranking Complexity Reusability	-	Partially Public	Small	-	[38]
PS9	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy Logic	Cost Time Others	-	-	-	-	[35]
PS10	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy Based MoSCoW	MoSCoW	-	Public	Medium	-	[5]
PS11	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy Logic	Dependency Others	-	Public	Medium	-	[41]
PS12	Fuzzy Logic	Goal-Based Fuzzy Grammar	Complexity Cost Others	-	Public	Medium	Complexity	[37]
PS13	Fuzzy Logic	Logarithmic Fuzzy Trapezoidal AHP	Others	-	-	-	-	[47]
PS14	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy Logic	Others	-	Public	Small	-	[14]
PS15	Fuzzy Logic	Trapezoidals Fuzzy	Ranking Business Value	-	-	-	-	[15]

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PS16	Fuzzy Logic	Fuzzy Linguistic Labels	Ranking Complexity Reusability	-	Public	Small	-	[40]
PS17	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Whale Optimization	Ranking Others	-	Private	-	Accuracy Disagreement	[10]
PS18	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Ant Colony	Ranking Cost Risk	-	Partially Public	Large	Time consumption Quality	[50]
PS19	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Particle Swarm	Ranking Dependency Business Value Others	-	Private	Medium	Time consumption Accuracy Disagreement	[23]
PS20	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Whale Optimization	Cost Business Value	-	Private	Large	Time consumption	[9]
PS21	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Whale Grey Wolf Optimization	Ranking	RALIC	Public	Medium	Accuracy	[25]
PS22	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Bee colony	Ranking Others	Greer and Ruhe/ Sagrado	Partially Public	Medium	Spread Hypervolume NDS	[8]
PS23	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Bee colony	Cost FR/NFR relation	-	-	-	Redundancy	[53]
PS24	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Reptile Search	Ranking Dependency Cost	-	-	-	-	[29]
PS25	BIO/Swarm Intelligence	Firefly	Ranking Others	-	Public	Small	Time consumption Disagreement Average Distance	[11]

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PS26	BIO/Evolutionary	Differential evolution	Ranking Dependency Cost Others	Greer and Ruhe/ Sagrado	Partially Public	Medium	Spread Hypervolume NDS	[17]
PS27	BIO/Evolutionary	IGA	Ranking Dependency	-	Private	Medium	Disagreement Average Distance	[52]
PS28	BIO/Evolutionary	EGA,RILP	Ranking Cost Time Business value	-	Private	Medium	-	[54]
PS29	BIO/Evolutionary	NSGA-IIPT	Ranking Cost Others	Greer and Ruhe/ Sagrado	Partially Public	Medium	Spread Hypervolume NDS	[32]
PS30	BIO/Evolutionary	VOP,GA	Ranking Dependency	-	Partially Public	Small	Disagreement Average Distance	[6]
PS31	ML/LRT/Pointwise	J48	Ranking	-	Private	-	User evaluation	[24]
PS32	ML/LRT/Pointwise	KNN	Ranking	-	Private	-	User evaluation/ Accuracy Precision Sensitivity	[7]
PS33	ML/LRT/Pointwise	K-means	Ranking Cost	RALIC	Public	Medium	Time Consumption/ Accuracy	[26]
PS34	ML/LRT/Pointwise	XGBoost LightGBM Lasso Regression SVM MLP Neural Network	Others	-	Private	Very Large	Precision Recall F1-score ROC-AUC	[16]

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PS35	ML/LRT/Pointwise	Decision Tree Random Forrest KNN Logistic Regression SVM	Ranking Dependency Time MoScow Others	-	Private	Large	Accuracy Precision Recall F1-score Time consumption k-fold cross validation	[22]
PS36	ML/LRT/Pointwise	k-means	Ranking	RALIC	Public	Medium	Mean square error ANOVA	[2]
PS37	ML/LRT/Pointwise	k-means	Others	-	Private	-	-	[43]
PS38	ML/LRT/Pairwise	PageRank	Ranking Dependency Cost Risk MoScow Business Value	-	Private	Large	Accuracy Time consumption	[1]
PS39	ML/LRT/Pairwise	Drank (PageRank, RankBoost)	Ranking Dependency Complexity Cost Risk Business Value Others	-	Private	Medium	User Evaluation/ TMR Time consumption IR	[45]
PS40	ML/LRT/Pairwise	CBRank (Priority Learning, RankBoost)	Ranking Others	-	Private	Medium	Disagreement	[39]
PS41	ML/LRT/Pairwise	GDRank (RankNet)	Ranking Others	-	Private	Small	Accuracy	[46]
PS42	ML/Others ML techniques	Inverse ML	Ranking Dependency Complexity Cost	-	Private	Medium	Accuracy Learning time MSE	[44]

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PS43	ML/Others ML techniques	Tensor	Ranking FR/NFR relation	-	Public	Medium	User Evaluation/ Accuracy Time consumption	[34]
PS44	ML/Others ML techniques	ARPT Dependency graph	Ranking Dependency	-	Private	Medium	Time Consumption MSE	[51]
PS45	Hybrid	Qubit function Brownboost rank	Ranking Dependency	PROMISE*	Public	Large	Time consumption Accuracy True Positive and False Positive rate	[20]
PS46	Hybrid	K-means Differential evolution	Ranking	RALIC	Public	Medium	ANOVA	[3]
PS47	Hybrid	Decision Tree Ranking Algorithm	Ranking Complexity Risk Time Cost MoSCoW	-	Private	-	User evaluation	[18]
PS48	Hybrid	Fuzzy c-means clustering Neural Network AHP	Ranking Business Value Others	-	Private	Large	Relative Performance	[12]
PS49	Hybrid	Neural network Fuzzy logic	Others	-	Public	Medium	Time consumption	[36]
PS50	Hybrid	Neural network LOG FAHP	Others	-	-	-	-	[48]
PS51	Hybrid	NLP SMT	Ranking Dependency Others	-	Private	Medium	User evaluation	[33]
PS52	Hybrid	LFTA ANN	Others	-	-	-	-	[49]

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				Name	Public/Private	Size		
PS53	Technique comparisons	QEMEA QMDEA MQHDE	Ranking Cost	-	Private	Large	Pareto optimal front Generational Distance Spread Hypervolume	[30]
PS54	Technique comparisons	AHP ANP FuzzyAHP FuzzyANP IGA	Ranking Cost Risk	-	Private	Medium	Accuracy Time consumption	[27]

Legend: *PROMISE dataset only provides classification and lacks ratings or importance measures.

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